

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

All right. Hello. Thank you so much for taking your time to be part of this interview. My name is Anna Makarudze, and I'm pursuing a master in software engineering and playing in digital technology and currently investigating developers' perspective on vulnerabilities in the open source dependencies they use in their project. And I'm focusing on five web frameworks, Django, next to TS, Springboot, Laravel, and Ruby on Rails. And our participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can draw from the interview at any time. It will not retain any personnel data or identifiable information.

The name, role, e-mail address, and unidentifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone. You can skip any questions you're not comfortable answering, and the responses will remain anonymous and do not be linked to you. And the interviews are only recorded and kept for the duration to allow the supervisors to verify the authenticity of the recorded data. And we comply with GDPR requirements.

So before we start, maybe you can introduce yourself, mention the projects that you are involved with, the developer, contributor, or maintainer. And also mention your level of experience in the software development industry. each framework you use and your level of experience with the framework.

Speaker 2

Yeah, for sure.

Once again, thank you so much for for having me as well. So the name is ... and currently I'm working as a data engineer for a venture capitalist company based in in Europe. So there, my main task is maintaining the data pipeline and building the company's data lake. And the main tech stack that we're using is Python Django and Next.js Reacts, which is hosted on a Linux infrastructure, so all on GCP or Google Cloud.

I started that. That's my latest role. I started it earlier this year, so that's January. And before that, I was working as a lead developer for an NGO in Mombasa, Kenya. It's called

Sahili Porter Foundation. So there, I was in charge of maintaining and building the internal platforms, internal data management tools, the ERP, and of course, their websites for external communications.

And the main stack there as well, it was Python Django, React, Next.js, and React Native for the mobile, for the mobile application on Android and iOS. So I've been working for Swahili Port for close to four years before I left. And before that, I was working, I was working as an intern for the local county government, that is Mombasa County, where my main role was, again, maintaining the county websites. So the public websites, the portals for e-services, So that is packing payments, tickets, payments, and, you know, booking appointment to the county offices and all of that.

And that was running on PHP. Yeah.

00:03:34 Speaker 1

Thank you. So in your current role. What is it that you actually do? For example, do you contribute code? Are you a tester? Do you, if you pull requests, make pull requests?

00:03:56 Speaker 2

Yeah, so I do both. In as much as I'm under a team lead, my co-task will be mainly fixing code issues, adding new pipelines to the code base, peer-to-peer review of my colleagues pull request, And again, quality check of the code bases that my colleagues have done, done that I've done.

So it's an all round, it's an all round task. And again, I also maintain the data pipeline which runs separately. So this means from data ingestions into the data lake that you have for the company to making sure that the data is synced. So the company is a financial, it's financial related.

So There's ingestion of new data, the syncing of data almost every day, close of, you know, business. So again, making sure that everything is well synced, everything is well updated without causing any breakages and triggering all other flows. So this again means all the automated tools are interacting safely and well with the code base to make sure that everything is up to date. And then as part of the company policy, it's We have a mandate to do like open source contribution to any Python projects that one feels like.

So this is, it's always tracks every month. So in as much as the company mandate have been doing that before, so it's not that kind of a big deal. So it's now looking for any open source project that we'll find online contributing to it. It doesn't need to be like a very huge

project or of very widely used, something that I see that I can put in some effort and, you know, and do something productive to it.

00:05:55 Speaker 1

So you're working for a corporate company, but sometimes you do maintain open source projects in the Python ecosystem.

Speaker 2

Yes.

Speaker 1

Okay. And how are security issues reported in your project?

Speaker 2

So we have two ways to do that. And the first one is using, there's this tool called GitGuardian. So GitGuardian will do like a full code scan of a PR that has been submitted or a commit that has been pushed to GitHub. So this will basically check for any leaked API keys or leaked confidentials. But GitGuard only does like a high level, high level kind of checks.

So the other one is we do have tests that do test code bases or pull requests to make sure that there is at least the minimum threshold of security on our code. So the first one is checking for any credentials or if there's any. packets being sent via sockets if it's well encrypted. And then of course we do also have a Q&A on board who regularly checks for the quality of the work done. And this checks also include security checks. And security checks also involves looking at types of third party packages or third party libraries that we're using.

Are they safe enough? Are they putting, will they put our project at risk in the near future or what are their status currently as well. Okay.

Speaker 1

And how conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your project?

Speaker 2

Pardon.

Speaker 1

How aware are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependencies present to your project?

Speaker 2

I don't put too much focus into it because you know there's someone handling that. But it's it's also it's also it's also an important thing that I'm aware of, you know, the libraries and the patches that I use in terms of how safe they are, how secure they are, how regularly are they updated, or if they have any security issues on their GitHub that needs to be handled.

Is it something big or is it something that I can, you know, I can assume will be well? So I don't know that much, but I do try and keep up as much as possible by checking the you know, just a regular random check to make sure everything is safe before using it.

Speaker 1

And how aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects, particularly that the dependencies can be used to launch supply chain attacks to your system?

Speaker 2

Using AI.

Speaker 1

I'm saying, how aware are you of supply chain attacks and their effects on software development projects?

Speaker 2

Not that much. Yeah. No, it's all right.

Speaker 1

And okay, you said, how do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your projects?

Speaker 2

How do I identify dependencies?

Speaker 1

With vulnerabilities in your project?

Speaker 1

I would watch to, yeah.

Speaker 2

So there's this GitGuardian tool. which does automatic checks and then there is the manual checks that I'll just randomly do myself. And this is like the due diligence. So this is if the project, if the, dependencies are open source, I'll go to the, you know, GitHub pages, check for any security vulnerabilities, check for any GitHub issues that do have, you know, any keywords related to security and see, and try to weigh if it's...

If it's if it's crucial enough for me to to ignore them, or if it's something that really needs to be taken into consideration.

Speaker 1

And what influences the decision to update to newer versions of dependent within your project? You just update your version or?

Speaker 2

So most of the time is yeah, we would love to to be, you know, using the latest versions because it's, normal for latest version to fix security issues or any other issue that they are handling. But we don't have like a specific guideline that will follow to just confirm if the update is okay or not.

I mean, as long as we're using it, we fully trust on it. So we just go there blindly and updating it and see what happens next. Okay.

Speaker 1

How do you check the maintenance of dependencies in your projects? Because with open source dependencies, it can happen, but the package can be taken over and it can be taken over by malicious actors. And when you do an update, you're actually, you are introducing vulnerabilities to your project. So how do you check the maintenance of dependencies in the project, given that we just trust it blindly to an update to new agents?

Speaker 2

Yeah, So there's, I mean, there are some of the packages that are really crucial to us. So what we do is we would really love to use them, but again, not highly rely on the open source side of it. So we would like clone the project into our own organization repository and then put it on our own infrastructure and then closely monitor any updates from the open source, test it, if it makes sense.

We now update the one that we learned from, but this only applies to a very few packages that we do believe that they have high importance and we wouldn't want to juggle security operates on it.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Speaker 2

Honestly, I don't have a straight answer to this because each time there's like a new way to handle it. And there's also one time that we, or maybe there's also some times that we fully depend on the AI agents that we've set up because of time, time to fix, time needed to bring this, to patch the solutions.

And at some point, we'll get, we'll outsource some, security analysts to go through a few packages to see if it's, really worth to keep it up.

But most of the time is highly relying on our AI agents, especially if it's something that will really need a short turnaround time to get it fixed and working.

Speaker 1

And how long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

It depends with the dependency. If it's something that's of really high importance, you have less than a day to do the fixes. But if it's something that you can easily find an alternative and then it's not that frequently used, we have we have like a seven, like a five, sorry, a five-day fixing period for us to find an alternative solution or fix the issue.

Speaker 1

Okay. And how do you handle the situation when the vulnerable dependent is no longer being maintained and there's no new version to update to? Like is it now it did packet?Yeah.

Speaker 2

So the other option will be looking for alternative dependencies that will, fit the description. But in that case, we've haven't, we haven't like dealt with it directly, but it's something that we've foreseen. So the fixes is, so the first step is looking for any alternatives that will closely fit to the description or to the correct or to the features of the dependency that we're using. The second option would be quickly spinning up something similar and that

would take time. So the quickest fix is getting an alternative or the other one is like looking for other ways to like work around without using the dependency itself.

Speaker 1

Okay, so one thing that I've observed being...from being a Django developer myself, is that some ecosystems like in the jungle community, they tend to take over projects they think they are useful after mundane has abandoned them, like just mundane that same with newly introduced jungle commons. So I'm wondering, is it a common practice for in the next years? ecosystem to take over projects that are not being maintained or people just move on to other projects.

Speaker 2

Yeah, yeah, I think it's it's going to become a very common thing because we've done that for a couple of dependencies and packages. And it's it's really helpful or useful to to know that we are way in charge or we we we can oversee what's happening with the packages in terms of maintenance, who is doing the maintenance.

Where is it posted that? So I know for sure this is going to be something that most companies will adopt. There's, of course, now that you have AI agents doing almost everything without a human in the loop. So to avoid such risky code performances or risky vulnerabilities. I just have anyone contributing though, checking for quality and stuff.

So the companies that really utilize these dependencies are adoption. I know that for sure because you have for a couple of dependencies, especially in the finance sector where we cater for the infrastructure, we cater for the maintenance just to make sure that it is safe for us to use and also for the partners that we have.

00:16:46 Speaker 1

Okay. And what challenges do you face in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your projects?

Speaker 2

I think the main challenge will be in as much as we want to address that we might not have like a full understanding of, you know, of the code base of a deeper infrastructure of how it works. So sometimes a fix could be as easy as doing something on the high level, but there could be a core issue, maybe some reliance packages or third parties on the dependencies are long overdue maintenance or maybe are not maintained anymore.

So getting to the core of that will take a lot of time. And then, of course, in the long run, delay some production features. And again, of course, would cause us to look for alternatives and all that.

Speaker 1

And what helps you to address vulnerable dependencies in your projects? Or what make it easier for you to address the vulnerabilities with vulnerable dependency in a project?

Speaker 2

I really want to say AI, but it's not. I mean, there's no way to say that something helps us for sure, because every time something comes up, it's completely new. We've never handled it before. So there's no specific method. But using tools like issue trackers, Sentry, GitGuardian, and other code scanning tools that we use will really help us to identify vulnerability issues, either in advance or try to troubleshoot what's happening currently. But I'm not sure of any like it's well documented procedures for us.

Speaker 1

And okay, I know, I know some frameworks are moving towards making sure that they have at least most of the common functionality in within the framework and that yeah, they don't rely on dependencies. And if they have any dependencies, they mandate them. How is Next.js with regards to it? Does it rely on a lot of dependence or is everything within Next.js itself?

Speaker 2

So for Next.js, what I love about them is they, if they identify a dependency that is highly used by, you know, by the ecosystem, they do take over the maintenance. So, which is, I think, it's really helpful for the developer itself. It reduces the burden of me checking if this dependency is okay, if this dependency is not okay, but this only works for those dependencies that the organization behind Next.js handles. And for the other things, it's a very, it's kind of like a gamble. There's no straightforward way to do that, if that makes sense.

Speaker 1

And okay, it's an opinion that is out there that JavaScript, because there are so many libraries, they teach to small things. And due to the compromises that have been happening on NPM, most developers associate JavaScript libraries with a lot of risks. And since you use Next.js, what's your opinion on that and how do you And all the risk that is that comes with you with using JavaScript libraries from NPM.

Speaker 2

Yeah, that's a very big challenge. Of course. There's there's almost anything or almost everything that you need out there, especially in terms of packages that would be available on NPM. But again, this is.

It's something that I personally have to weigh my options if I really need to use a third-party dependencies that is available on NPM or not. Of course, doing a background check of who's maintaining it, who is handling it, that could take time, and of course, sometimes it's strict deadlines.

You have no time for that, so... it's a very low-hanging fruit, but I personally love to, if it's something that I can quickly create something by myself without relying on the dependencies, I'd quickly do it because I personally don't trust, I'd say 80% of whatever dependencies that they're on NPM because, you know, anybody and anyone can contribute to those packages without a proper... security check without a proper background check, reviews and all that.

So this will potentially bring vulnerabilities to the platform, so the system that you build. So my simple take here is if I'm not sure of the package or the dependency, I'll quickly spin up something that I can use, even if it takes longer, but it's safe in the long run.

Speaker 1

All right, but do you... verify the background and maintenance of dependence that you're using in your dependency tree.

Speaker 2

Yeah, for for large projects. I I do. I do verify that. But if it's for for simple, simple projects that don't have like a long, longer running time. I I close my eyes and do whatever using packages. Alright.

Speaker 1

Do you have any recommendations for dependency management for open source

Speaker 2

Any recommendations? Let me check if this is the ones we use. Nah, not that I know of often. I I do have to check on on our company docs, and then I can share something with you. Maybe after this?

Speaker 1

Alright.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much. That's all from me. Thank you for taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

Thank you. I also appreciate the call. It's It's it's it's triggering thoughts and dependencies issues. I know that that I was not not checking into that. So this this also really helps. I appreciate.

Speaker 1

Yeah, you're welcome. Thank you so much.

Speaker 2

Thank you.